

**XInfluence of geometric parameters of the flow fields on the
performance of a PEM fuel cell. A review**

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Abstract

The proton Exchange membrane fuel cell (PEMFC) performance depends not only on many factors including the operation conditions, transport phenomena inside the cell and kinetics of the electrochemical reactions, but also in its physical components; membrane electrode assembling (MEA) and bipolar plates (BPs). Among the PEM stack components, bipolar plates are considered one of the crucial ones, as they provide one of the most important issues regarding the performance of a stack, the homogeneous distribution of the reactive gases all over the catalyst surface and bipolar plate areas through, the so call, flow channels; physical flow patterns or paths fabricated on the

BPs surfaces to guide the gases all along the BPs for its correct distribution. The failure in flow distribution among different unit cells may severely influence the fuel cell stack performance. Thus, to overcome such possible failures, the design of more efficient flow channels has received considerable attention in the research community for the last decade.

The aim of this work is to review the most important results conducted in recent years related to the influence of the different geometric parameters of the flow channels on the overall performance of a PEMFC.

1. Introduction

Due to the increasing world concern about the environmental pollution and the depletion of fossil fuel reserves, the solutions for the generation of clean energy are an urgent demand. In the last decade, fuel cells appear to be one of the most suitable alternatives for generation of clean energy and, among them, PEM fuel cells seem to be one of the most reliable ones. Some of the PEMFC advantages with regard to other types of fuel cells are their easy implementation and their longer lifetime. Furthermore, their low operation temperature, high power density, fast start-ups, soundness of the system and low emission have encouraged the interest of various industry sectors to open up new fields of application for these fuel cells, including the motor industry, the stationary power generation, portable applications, etc. [1]. Currently, many

research efforts focus on the development of more efficient PEMFC that produce high current densities for longer operational periods [2].

Although there are many factors involved in the performance of a PEMFC (such as the operating conditions, the transport phenomena, the kinetics of the electrochemical reaction or the assembling of the MEA), a fuel cell stack performance is simply the sum of the performance of individual cells. This correlation is not achieved in practice due to different reasons including maldistribution of reactants among different cells of the stack. The effects of a poor or maldistribution of reactants in PEM stack flow fields is considered a crucial issue to be taken into account, as it leads to non-uniform current density, localized hot spots in the membrane, performance degradation, and material degradation [3]. On the contrary, a uniform distribution of current density leads to uniform distribution of temperature and liquid water production, and lower mechanical stresses on the MEA. Although the problem has been addressed largely through numerical simulation, experimental data and an insight into the factors responsible for maldistribution continue to be an area of interest.

In general maldistribution in parallel channels may be caused, among others, by uneven flow resistances in the parallel channels caused by variations in channel dimensions, different flow lengths, uneven fouling, density and viscosity variations, and presence of two or more phases due to water content in the channels [4]. The lack of an experimental technique to measure the instantaneous flow distribution is something that needs to

be overcome, although it may represent an extremely difficult issue for PEM stacks systems. However, numerical attempts were attained by Ganesh et al. and Bansode et al. [5,6], who simulated the flow distribution in a PEM stack by using flow channelling theory to analyze flow maldistribution. Their investigations showed how the variation in port diameter led to different grades of gas maldistribution and consequently, non-uniform water content in the membrane. Other researchers [7,8] have focused their numerical studies to evaluate the influence of the flow field geometry on the pressure drop variation and flow distribution in a PEM stack. They concluded that both the channel resistance and the rip widths (space between channels) can enhance the uniformity of the flow distribution. However larger rip width may constitute a better solution for flow distribution because increasing the channel resistance requires an excessive pressure drop which is not beneficial in practical applications.

This maldistribution of the different gases among BPs is one of the multiple consequences concerning the flow field design. Thus, another immediate consequence derived from such behaviour is the flooding effect. This effect is a result of water accumulation in the flow channels (resulting from product water or/and vapour condensation) both in the catalyst layer (CL) (micro and/or macro sized layers) and the GDL. This water accumulation leads to a two-phase flow pattern which may affect the flow rates and the flow under rips [9].

The extremely great amount of both, parameters and phenomenon, involved in the relation between the PEMFC performance and flow

field designs makes it crucial to dedicate more and more numerical and experimental research in order to establish optimal geometric configurations that allow enhancing the energy production in the PEMFC, thus increasing its lifetime.

In Aiyejina and Sastry [10] work, the authors present a thorough review on the mathematical modelling of PEMFC flow channel geometry, in order to improve of PEMFC performance. Also, some recommendations that can be implemented in optimizing the design of PEMFC flow fields for maximum performance are mentioned. Thus conclusions show that a serpentine flow field with small channel and rib size would perform the best at low operating voltages. Besides, it has been concluded that additions such baffles improve the performance of different types of flow channel designs.

2. Flow field

Bipolar plates are one of the key components of a fuel cell, since they perform different functions that are essential for an effective performance of the system. Although some of these functions are better associated with physical-chemical and fluid-dynamic phenomenon, they are closely related with the BPs themselves, and with the flow channel geometry in particular. Thus, they provide the necessary mechanical support for the stack, keep the different reactants isolated from each other distributing them on the catalyst surface of the MEA through the gas diffusion layer, and help to manage the water and heat

generated inside the cell. Therefore their design can reach a significant impact on the performance and power density obtained from a PEMFC. Increases up to 50% in produced power density have been described only with an optimal design of the flow field of reactants [11,12].

An increased amount of different flow field geometric configurations can be recently found in literature. Each of these geometrics configurations show advantages and disadvantages depending on the PEMFC operating conditions for which they were designed [13].

Figs. 1 and 2 show some of the most studied settings:

- Serpentine flow field (simple or multiple)
- Straight parallel flow field or Z-type parallel configuration
- Interdigitated flow field
- Pin or mesh flow field
- Cascade flow field

The straight parallel version is the simplest one requiring the smallest pressure drop by equally distributing the flow rate into many parallel paths. However, if the flow resistance is not maintained at the same level in each parallel flow channel a non-uniform distribution of the reactants may occur. In order to solve such possible maldistribution of the reactants, serpentine flow field geometry has been proposed. In this design the reactant gas is forced to flow through a single path which may consist of one or more flow channels that extent over the entire active surface area. This configuration increases both, the flow

speed and the pressure drop enhancing water and heat management by transporting the two-phase water through the channels.

Interdigitated flow fields are based on dead-end channel designs which lead the gases toward the GDLs by means of under-rip paths. This provokes a convective flow under the rip which enhances an effective utilization of the catalysts by facilitating liquid water removal in those regions [14-16]. The role of under-rip convection in PEMFC was also numerically studied by Jin Hyun Nam et al. [17]. The results showed that maximum path-length difference between neighbouring flow-channels was expected to enhance under-rib convection and transport, thereby improving the performance of PEMFCs.

The pin-type flow field consist of columnar pins (generally cubical or circular) arranged in a regular pattern. As the reactants flow through a network of series and parallel flow paths only low pressure drops occur. However, this leads to inhomogeneous gas distribution or reactant maldistribution and locally flooding and heating phenomenon. The cascade design consist of a number of slots arranged in parallel which present a plurality of stages or plateaus, each of which has an upper surface which terminates in a pair of corresponding passage (the open cavity). On each plateau of the cascade, the flow splits so that in essence half of it will flow towards each of the slots at the edge of the corresponding plateau being directed downward and so reaching the GDL and the CL. The initial flow distribution within the cascade region splits the flow a number of times, with each path being equal in length and geometry so that the flow rates and pressure drops are substantially the

same, and the arrival time of the fuel/air interface during startup, or change in fuel flow rate during transient conditions, is substantially simultaneous at each of the cascade outlet slots. However, the main drawbacks in this flow field design are the difference in reactant degrees of penetration and the high pressure drop as the flow develops.

Much Research has been carried out concerning the influence of the flow field design in the performance of PEMFCs. Once the decision of which type of flow field geometry is going to be studied, the type of flow field is a variable that keeps constant. Thus, the study of the influence of the flow field design in the efficiency of PEMFCs is achieved by studying the PEMFC response to different operating conditions created by changing variables such as the operating temperature, relative humidity, the pressure of the reagents, the flow direction, etc are setup. Hwang [18] analysed the influence of the of operation temperature on the performance of the PEMFC using plates with 25 cm² of active area, with single serpentine type flow fields, in which the channel to rib width ratio remained constant. Water management in the polymeric electrolyte membrane is essential to obtain the maximum power of a PEM type fuel cell as a complete hydration is required to allow good proton conduction. However, for low temperatures PEMFC and under certain operating conditions; high humidification of the reactants, and high current densities, the gases inside the cells become oversaturated with water vapour which may condense in the cathode side, resulting in a lower power output. Hydration of

the MEAs can be achieved by moisturizing the reactive flows. On the other hand, water is generated internally at the cathode side as a result of the electrochemical reaction (OOR). Striking a balance between the quantity of water produced and the necessary to obtain a good proton conduction, removing the excess properly to avoid the flood of channel flow or flooding effect [19], has been the aim of many studies. It should also be emphasized that in addition to the flow channel layout, channel dimensions and cross-section geometry also influence water removal and cell performance [20].

Shimpalee et al. [21] studied the influence of the relative humidity of the cathode reagents in the performance of a fuel cell with 480 cm² of active area, with multiple serpentine flow channels (selected from US patent literature) by means of a three-dimensional fluid dynamic simulation using parallel computing techniques. The distribution of pressure, temperature and electrochemical variables for stationary (humidified cathode) and automotive (dry cathode) operating conditions are examined. They found that in both cases the power output did not show significant difference. However, from an electrochemical point of view, the humidified cathode condition showed higher overall performance than the dry condition due to the dehydration of the membrane which increased its ohmic loss across the MEA. They also found that although in the dry version the pressure drop inside the PEMFC could be reduced by 30%, this kept unchanged for the humidified version.

Li et al. [22] proposed a serpentine flow field design (Fig. 3) that would set the appropriate pressure drop along the channel flow so that any liquid water generated inside the cell will be eliminated or evaporated through gas streams, thus preventing PEMFC malfunction by flooding. At the same time, the gas flow in the flow channel was kept completely saturated in order to prevent the membrane dehydration. Trials have been conducted with flow fields of 50, 100, 200, 300 and 441 cm², concluding that a serpentine channel configuration can provide an excellent cell performance, due to their ability to compensate the elimination of water at an acceptable pressure drop, as no liquid water content was observed in the cell by the neutron imaging technique.

Wang and Liu [23] used a interdigitated flow field of 50 cm² active area to study the effect that the fuel cell temperature, the humidification of the reagents, the pressure of the gases and stoichiometry had over the PEMFC performance. Hsieh [24] compared the effects of different parameters on three flow fields of 5 cm² with three different geometries (Fig. 4): serpentine, interdigitated and mesh or pin type. They reported similar behaviours for all the microcells regarding variations in temperature and back pressure and confirmed that such behaviours were similar to those expected for a conventional PEMFC. They concluded that the flow field with interdigitated type channels yielded a better performance, although a lower pressure drop was found for mesh type flow channels at a fixed active area of the MEA.

Several works focused on the comparison between the performance of parallel flow fields and interdigitated flow fields [25], proposing either different geometries (NINO [26]) or the use of porous materials such as foam as outflow channels [27]. In [28] and [29], flow fields with an active area of 198 cm^2 with parallel, serpentine and interdigitated type channels were used. It was found that the former flow field design displayed better performance than the parallel flow field as it forces reactive gases to pass through gas diffusion layers (GDLs) (Fig. 5). In addition, it was shown that a fuel cell with interdigitated flow field can perform similarly to another cell with parallel channels geometry, but with a lower fuel consumption. On the other hand, regarding the serpentine flow fields, it was shown that increasing the number of channels, channel length and the number of turns, favours the electrochemical reaction, reducing unreacted fuel at the exit and, therefore, increasing the fuel cell performance.

In Kumar y Reddy [30] work, serpentine, parallel, multi-parallel and discontinuous flow channels were analysed at PEMFC voltage values of 0.66, 0.64, 0.68 and 0.71 V, respectively, and a fixed current density of 5000 A m^{-2} , to study the steady and transient (by changing the load level current from 5000 to 8000 Am^{-2}) behaviour of the PEM fuel cell. This work shows that in a steady state PEMFC performance the discontinuous design will perform better than the other three designs. The reason is that the discontinuity of the channels forced the gas into the GDL, thus converting the transfer of reactant through the GDL from

diffusion to diffusion and convective, and thereby, increasing the local effective pressure of reactant at the reaction interface. However, it was found that the best PEMFC performance in transient response was for the parallel flow field design, showing the lower performance in a steady-state conduct. Thus This study determined that the use of the design is closely related to the type of PEMFC application.

A comparative study of simple serpentine, multiple serpentine, simple parallel, parallel type U, symmetrical in U, parallel in series and interdigitated flow fields [31](Fig. 6), reflected that geometric configurations with smaller pressure drop present high a non-uniformity behaviour. In other words, geometric configurations that showed large surface active areas (narrow ribs) do not receive sufficient amounts of reactants because of their maldistribution. Therefore, although pressure drop in a fuel cell is one of the major determinants of its global efficiency, homogeneous distribution of reactants on the active area is essential to obtain an optimal cell performance.

The comparative analysis of different flow field geometric configuration is repeated in multiple studies, both in steady state [32-52], and in transient state [53,54]. The following conclusions can be drawn from these analyses:

- The flow field geometric configuration has little influence on the cell performance at high operation potentials. On the contrary, at low operation potentials, where

concentration losses or mass transport are the main determining factor in PEMFC performance, geometric configuration significantly affects.

- Flow fields with lower pressure drops (straight parallel or Z-type parallel, pin-type and cascade) generally allow preferential flow paths, favouring reagent maldistribution over the active surface area of the MEA and, therefore, decreasing electrochemical reaction efficiency and PEMFC performance.
- Serpentine and interdigitated flow fields enhance uniform reactants distribution over the catalytic layers, increasing both, the current density values and performance of the cell. On the contrary, higher pressure drop to the gas flow passage are developed, increasing the energy required to drag the gas, which reduces the global performance of the system. However, this increase in the pressure drop within the flow field promotes convective flow or under rib flow, improving the elimination of the residual water in the cathode side, increasing the overall efficiency of the electrochemical reaction, and thus, the current density obtained.
- In serpentine type flow fields, longer straight channels and segments between channel, bends and narrower channels enhance convective flow, improving the performance of the cell. Likewise, square channel bends provoke higher pressure drop compared to curvilinear channel bends.
- One of the main concerns of the BPs designers is to prevent the flooding effect in the cathode. Therefore, the

application of different geometries in the anodic and cathodic sides of the PEMFC is advisable. Generally, geometries with higher pressure drop (serpentine and interdigitated) that enhance convective flow are used for the cathode, because they help to eliminate excess water, also improving the efficiency of the electrochemical reaction.

- Generally, increasing the cell active area decreases the current density values obtained.
- For fuel cell operating on oxygen, the rib width of the flow fields should be wider than that used in fuel cell operating on air.

3. Flow direction

During the operation of a PEM fuel cell, the reactants circulate along the flow channels where reactants conditions (pressure, concentration, temperature, relative humidity, etc.) vary significantly as flowing from the gas inlet to the outlet. Therefore, the direction follow by reactants through the cell on both sides of the MEA will determine the conditions of the gases at different points of the flow path. The circulation settings of the reactive gases most analysed are: co-flow, counter flow and cross flow.

In Ge and Yi work [55] the influence of the reactants flow direction in 140 cm² active area PEM fuel cell performance was studied. Results of this work showed improvement in membrane

humidification when a counter flow layout was proposed. Also, uniform current density distribution all over the active area of the MEA was developed, so avoiding localized hot spots and increasing the performance of the fuel cell. Scholta et al. [56] analysed PEMFC performance for different configurations in the anodic and cathodic direction flow using dry gas in the anode and humid gas in the cathode, e.i. co-flow, counter flow and cross flow (Fig. 7). Bipolar plates, with 100 cm² active area and simple serpentine flow fields were used. In this work, counter flow configuration also showed better PEMFC performance mainly due to a more even humidity distribution in the cell. Concerning the fuel cell performance with parallel flow field designs, setting a similar counter flow configuration, it was found that flow fields having a large depth also showed higher cell voltages, if high current densities were applied. This behaviour was attributed to a reduction of cross transport with respect to lower pressure differences. Besides, it was shown that when increasing the number of parallel channels the cell voltage decreased when working at low reactant demand. This behaviour is contrary to that observed when highly parallel channels were used at high current densities. Larger depths are showing also a higher cell voltage, especially if high current densities are applied. Thus, to conclude with, the authors confirm that that number of parallel channels depends not only on flow field dimensions and geometries, but also on the PEMFC operation range.

Morin et al. [57] investigated the influence of the flow direction on the water management in a PEMFC. Results showed that PEMFCs with counter flow layout better membrane hydration is obtained, increasing proton conductivity and, therefore, the performance of the cell. Besides, they found that the effect of gravity allows water retention in the cell, which also enhanced membrane hydration.

Valiño et al. [58] analysed the performance of a cell with cascade flow fields with 100 cm² active area (Fig. 8). Different configurations in the flow direction were studied: co-flow, counter flow and cross flow. The main results showed that the consumption of the reactants on the catalytic layers mainly depends on the gas flow with stoichiometric defect, which is usually hydrogen, and not on the configuration of the flow direction. Distribution of the reactants throughout the flow field yielded non-uniform electrochemical reaction over the catalyst layer. Most of the electrochemical reactions took place near the hydrogen inlet, so that a very significant part of the active area was underused.

4. Channel length and number of channels

Channel length and the number of channels are two of the most influential geometric parameters on the fuel cell performance, especially in serpentine flow fields. Several studies analysed the reactants convective flow under the rib [59,60]. The former work concludes that, in single-serpentine flow field geometry, the percentage of flow travelling through the GDL is directly

related to the material and geometric parameters of the BPs. Moreover, it was found that GDL thickness slightly affected convection. Also, it was confirmed that convective flow increases by increasing the length of the flow channels. Thus employing rectangular rather than square active areas may be advantageous in order to enhance PEMFC performance. The latter work (Fig. 9) shows that varying the path length of the PEMFC by changing the number of parallel channels can affect its performance, FIG. Thus, PEMFC with shorter path lengths showed more uniform current density distribution and less flooding effect than with longer paths. However, an overall performance of the PEMFC with 13-channel flow field showed slight enhancement compare to the 26-channel PEMFC flow field. The cause was the small difference in membranes hydration. An increase in the number of channels from 13 up to 26 uniformly distributed the current density and temperature values under the ribs, compared to those values achieved under the channels. This behaviour increases the membrane water content due to reduction of saturation pressure of water, thus enhancing local performance and, therefore, the overall PEMFC performance.

5. Use of baffles in the gas flow direction

Reactants flowing along the flow channels reach the GDL of the MEA and then, through it, the gases diffuse to reach the catalytic layers where the electrochemical reactions occur. On the other hand, part of the reactants flow away from the gas

diffusion layers and do not participate in such reactions. As a consequence, concentration losses and the amount of unreacted gas at the outlet of the cell increase, which reduces the efficiency of the system.

Since the surface of the flow channels that is in contact with the diffusion layers can represent less than 60% of the total reactive surface of the cell, it is crucial to enhance convective flow (Fig. 10), so that the fraction of reactive gas and, therefore, the efficiency of the cell increases. Also, water remove is expected to be bettered.

The convective flow under rib can be enhanced by increasing the pressure in adjacent channels of a serpentine flow field BP topology [59,60] **Error! Bookmark not defined.** Also, the use of baffles in the flow channels has demonstrated to be an effective way to increase the amount of gas that reaches the catalytic layers and reacts.

Besides the already mention flow field designs, there are some other studies that show novel flow field topologies [61-63], for example, baffle-blocked flow fields were designed to force more reactant in the flow channel enter the GDL and catalyst layer. Studies of PEMFC performance combining baffled flow field designs with other parameters such as the variation in the number of channels have also been develop [64]. Results showed that baffles forced reactant flow through the GDL to the catalyst layer, which implied increase of effective active area.

However the degree of current density increase at low voltages decreases as the number of baffles increases, which implies that there is an optimum number of baffles that enhance PEMFC performance.

The effects of baffle-blocked flow channel design on the PEMFC performance was also analysed by In Yan et al. [65] in 198.81 cm² active area fuel cell. Three different BP topologies (Fig. 11) were used in the cathode side (conventional parallel flow field, interdigitated flow field I with a baffle located at one end of each path, and interdigitated flow field II with baffles located at the mid-way/ends of each flow path). For each flow field design three flow area ratios (the ratio of the flow channel area to the total reacting area of BPs) of 60.22% (1.2/0.8), 50.75% (1/1) and 40.23% (0.8/1.2), were tested. Results showed that PEM fuel cells with the interdigitated flow fields I and II (Fig. 11) perform better than that with the parallel flow field design, demonstrating that the blockage effect due to baffles in the flow channels enhances the fuel gas transport and, in turn, increases the cell performance. The effect of oxygen flow rate on PEMFC performance was also studied. Results showed that the PEM fuel cells with conventional flow channels performed more efficiently as the oxygen flow rate was increased from 400 cm³ min⁻¹ to 1000 cm³ min⁻¹ whereas further increases had little influence in the PEMFC performance. On the contrary, PEM fuel cells with interdigitated I and II flow fields displayed better PEM fuel cell performance as the effects of the oxygen flow rates had slightly modified

its conduct when reaching flow rates of $600 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$ and $400 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$, respectively. They also noted that a voltage drop happened at the so-called limiting current for each flow area ratio when oxygen flow was $400 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$, but it begun negligible when the oxygen flow rate exceeded $600 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$. Thus with higher flow rates $1000 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$ PEM fuel cell with flow area ratio of 50,75% showed the best performance reaching a cell power output of 77 W, compare to those obtained 71 W and 67W with cell with flow area ratios of 40.23% and 60.22%, respectively.

In Thitakamol et al. [66] the performance of a PEM fuel cell with a mid-baffle interdigitated cathode flow field with 50.41 cm^2 active area was experimentally investigated (Fig. 12). Results were compared to those of a conventional interdigitated flow field. In both cases, a conventional interdigitated flow field was placed in the anode. When the oxidant reactant gas was oxygen, both geometries presented a similar performance. On the other hand, when air was used and depending on the air flow rate, the maximum power output of the mid-baffle interdigitated flow field was nearly 1.2-1.3 times that of the conventional one. Polarization curves in the latter case showed large limiting current densities at every flow rate used. Finally, the experimental study also demonstrated that increasing the oxidant gas flow rate and operating pressure, the PEMFC performance can be enhanced.

On the other hand, the effect that baffles have on transient response needs to be considered if quick response to sudden load

changes is demanded by the PEMFC operating condition. The baffled designs studied in Li et al. [54], showed significantly worse transient response compared to their no baffled counterparts.

6. Geometric parameters of the flow channel cross section

6.1 Cross section shape

Regarding the cross section shape of the channels, although channels with semicircular, trapezoidal, triangular, etc. sections have been studied, rectangular cross section has been the channel's most widely used configuration [67]. Kumar and Reddy [68] numerically analysed the effect of channel dimensions on the hydrogen consumption at the anode. For high hydrogen consumptions (80%), the optimum dimension values for channel width, rib width and channel depth was close to 1.5, 0.5 and 1.5 mm, respectively. Moreover, the effect of different channel shapes was investigated. Results showed that triangular and hemispherical shaped cross-section resulted in higher hydrogen consumption by around 9% at the anode, improving fuel cell efficiency.

In [69] three different channel cross sections were investigated: rectangular, trapezoidal and parallelogram (Fig. 13), on a straight flow channel at high current densities. The results showed the importance of the rib width on the cell

performance. Narrower rib width facilitates the distribution of reactants and helps to reduce concentration losses.

Results of the numerical simulations with these geometries revealed that the rectangular section channel provided higher cell potentials, whereas the trapezoidal cross section displayed more uniform current density distributions. On the other hand, this research indicated that cathode overpotential and ohmic losses were very sensitive to the rib width, whereas the cell operation potential was not influenced by the rib width for low current densities. However, at high operating current density, by contrast, there was an optimum channel-rib width ratio (1.3-1.4).

Owejan et al. [70] studied multiple serpentine PEMFC performance with flow fields of 50 cm² active area, cross flow configuration and 0.52 mm² rectangular and triangular cross section channels (Fig. 14). Variations were also made on the diffusion media properties (Toray and SGL gas diffusion layers) to evaluate the effects on the overall volume and spatial distribution of accumulated water. The study showed different in-plane permeability of the diffusion layers is responsible for the convective flow. Thus, Toray layers which showed the highest in-plane permeability enhanced gas water slugs, at low current densities. However SGL materials showed higher in-plane pressure drop, thus enhancing the convective removal of liquid water. Concerning the flow channels geometry, they concluded that triangular shape retains less water than rectangular channels of

the same cross-sectional area, and water is accumulated in the corners adjacent to the GDL.

Generally, the flow fields analysed in the laboratory have been mechanized with highly precise tools and processes, reason why its geometry keeps invariable, no matter the number of cells mechanized. However, in mass production processes, resulting geometry can display slight variations in relation to the original design. The magnitude of this variation will depend on the used manufacturing process. Shimpalee et al. [71] investigated the effect of channel tolerances on the PEMFC performance using different manufacturing processes. Results showed that when fabricating bipolar plates by chemical or electroetching, the effect of draft angle or etch factor really affected the PEMFC performance through changes in heat transport, uniformity in gas distributions and pressure drop.

6.2 Channel and rib width

Many researchers have analysed the influence of two essential geometric parameters; the channel and rib widths [72-76]. These studies have demonstrated that such values affect many of the operational PEMFC variables and thus, to its performance. They concluded that the influence of those parameters is more evident at low operation potentials and that, in each particular case, there is an optimal fuel cell configuration that maximizes the cell performance.

Scholta et al. [77] analysed a model of 100 cm² active area, with a parallel flow field and counter flow field. In this

study, the influence of channels and rib widths on the PEMFC performance was studied using a basic flow field design. Values between 0.7 and 1 mm were chosen as optimal values for either channel or rib widths. Generally, narrow channel dimensions are more appropriate for high current densities, whereas wider dimensions are better at low current densities.

Shimpalee and Van Zee [78], numerically investigated the influence of channel and rib width on PEMFC performance and reactants distribution on a 25 cm² fuel cell with serpentine flow field and different fuel flows configurations, for both automotive and stationary conditions (Fig. 15). The results showed that the performance was slightly higher for the narrower channel with wider rib spacing for stationary condition. Apparently, such configuration enhanced heat transfer from the MEA to ward collector as well as increased the pressure drop. On the other hand, it was observed how channel configuration with wider channels and narrower ribs provokes non-uniform local distribution of the reactants, although the global distribution of reactants kept uniform. It was also noted that the counter flow configuration showed much lower performance than the co-flow for both, automotive and stationary conditions.

Wang et al. [79] numerically analysed the effect of the cathode flow channel area ratio on a PEMFC with parallel and interdigitated flow channel designs, for five different flow channel area ratios (flow channel to total reaction area ratios): 0.3, 0.4 0.522, 0.6 and 0.7. Results showed that, for

parallel flow channel designs, fuel is driven into the GDL and CL mainly by diffusion. So that, the greater the flow channel area ratio was, the better the cell performance mainly due to the increase of the contact area between the fuel and the GDL. It was also found that for interdigitated flow channels the flow channel area ratio is not a critical value to be considered due to its less effect. The baffle configuration in the interdigitated flow fields forced the fuel into the porous layers enhancing fuel participation in the electrochemical reaction. This effect not only increased the fuel transport rates, but also enhanced the liquid water removal, increasing PEM fuel cell performance.

6.3 Channel depth

Few studies can be found in literature having investigated the influence of depth channel on the performance of a PEMFC. On the contrary, many of them have been focused on the analysis of other flow channel geometric parameters, such as the channel width varying the channel depth in order to keep a constant hydraulic diameter [68], although avoiding studying its effects.

In Yan et al. [80] a flow field of 198.87 cm² active area flow field, with tapered channel designs (tapered in height or width) was studied. The results showed that the application of tapered flow channel design in the bipolar plate of PEM fuel cells enhances fuel rates, fuel transport phenomena, the liquid water removal and, therefore, PEM fuel cell performance. Liu et al.

[81] numerically analysed the influence of the reduction in channel depth along the cathode streamwise direction (Fig. 16), noting that, for low operating voltages, this reduction forced more reactant gas into the gas diffuser layer and catalyst layer, which in turn resulted in a better cell performance.

On a multiple serpentine type flow field with 5.29 cm² active area, Yang et al. [82] investigated the influence of reduction of the outlet channel flow area reduction on PEM fuel cell performance and local transport phenomena (Fig. 17). They concluded that, the reactant transport, reactant utilization and liquid water removal were enhanced in comparison with a conventional serpentine flow field as the reduction of the outlet channel flow area was greater. Nevertheless, the pressure drop also increased, reducing the global performance of the cell. Concerning the pressure losses, the optimal PEMFC performance was obtained at a height contraction ratio of 0.4 (defined as H_C/H_0 ; Fig. 17) and a length contraction ratio of 0.4 (defined as L_C/L_0 ; Fig. 17).

In two similar works [83,84], an optimization method for a single serpentine PEM fuel cell, with 5 channels of 81 mm² active area, was proposed by varying the height flow channel (Fig. 18). This geometrical variable was only applied in the cathode, maintaining slightly similar the anode flow channel in order to keep a constant channel section. An optimized geometry allows an increase in the cell output power by 11.9 over that of a cell with straight channels. The optimal model is composed of

three tapered channels (channels 2-4) and a final diverging channel (channel 5). According to the authors, the convergent channels improve the main channel flow and sub-rib convection, both increasing the local oxygen transport rate and, hence, local electrical current density. Divergence of the channels, on the other hand, allows minimizing reactant leakage to the outlet.

Fontan et al. [85] analysed a model with identical anode and cathode geometry, composed of a single straight channel (1 mm wide, 50 mm long), varying the height of lateral walls progressively (Fig. 19). Results showed that a slope of 0.75° in the flow channel can produce an increase of almost 9.5% in the generated current density, and an increase of 8% in the obtained maximum power density. The main disadvantage in using non-uniform channels is the increase in pressure drop. The pressure drop in the flow channel is multiplied by a factor of 2 and 3.5 for inclinations of 0.5° and 0.75° , respectively.

6.4 Height to width ratio of the channel cross section:

In recent works the influence of the channel cross-section ratio (defined as the height to width ratio) on the PEM fuel cell performance is analysed in both, single and multiple serpentine channel flow field.

Choi et al. [86] studied the influence of different channel heights and widths on the performance of a PEMFC with multiple

serpentine flow field. Seven 25 cm² flow field patterns of 5-passes and 4-turns with different channel widths and heights (Fig. 20) were numerically simulated. The obtained results showed that as the channel height increases, the pressure drop is decreased because of the increase in cross-sectional area of the gas flow. This effect caused accumulation of liquid water at the outlet, slightly reducing the cell performance. On the other hand, as the channel width increases, the cell voltage decreases in large extent, compared to the cell voltage values observed when increasing the channel height. Membrane dehydration occurred with wider channel configurations, whereas the oxygen mass fraction in under-rib regions increased as convection was enhanced. Electrochemical reaction increased water content, however the actual channel configuration showed poor water removal affected by the lack of back diffusion effect.

A. P. Manso et al. [87] numerically analysed the influence of 10 different channel cross section ratios varying between 0.07 and 15 (Fig. 21) (height of channel C_H to width of channel C_W ratio) on the performance of a PEM fuel cell with serpentine flow field (SFF) design. In all cases the channel cross section area (1.06 mm²) and the total effective active area (256 mm²) of the PEM fuel cell were kept constant. Results showed that flow field designs with wider than higher sections ($C_H < C_W$), display less uniform current distributions, with lower maximum and minimum intensity values, temperature distributions with higher gradients and values, and a low water content in the membrane, which determines a lower global cell performance. On the other

hand, models with higher than wider sections ($C_H > C_W$) present more uniform current distributions, with higher maximum and minimum intensity values, temperature distributions with lower gradients and values, and a higher water content in the membrane, which allows a higher global cell performance. Finally, 10/06 and 12/05 channel cross section ratios present the best combination of variables, as shown by their polarisation curves.

7. New flow field geometries for bipolar plates

Besides the analysis of the influence of geometrical parameters using the most common flow field geometries on PEMFC performance, new studies are becoming increasingly involved in developing new flow field designs. These new geometries range from slight modifications of the already known geometries to completely different configurations.

Hu et al. [88] numerically analysed a new type of flow field, called slotted-interdigitated channel, based on interdigitated channel. In order to reduce the pressure drop of interdigitated flow channel, small slots were designed at the reactant flow field side. However, CFD simulation results showed that an arbitrary design of the slots causes severe flow maldistribution. To resolve this problem, the number of slots was decreased to two and alternatively positioned every two neighbouring channels. An analytical model was used to optimize the plate dimensions. Finally, even flow distribution was

obtained according to optimum results and high fuel cell performance was achieved.

Kuo et al. [89] performed a comparative study between a conventional straight gas flow channel and a novel wave-like gas flow channel (Fig. 22). Their results showed the appearance of convection effects in the wave-like channel. The results showed that compared to a straight gas flow channel, the wave-like channel provides an improved convective heat transfer performance, a higher gas flow rate and a more uniform temperature distribution. As a result, the efficiency of the catalytic reaction was greatly enhanced, with higher cell voltage and power density.

In order to improve water management in a PEMFC-slanted channels with an angle of 20° , Bunmark et al. [90] investigated the effects of orientations of the slanted channels in up-slanted and down-slanted directions. The experimental results showed that modification of the anode flow field using down-slanted channels improved PEM fuel cell performance. The fraction of liquid water on the anode was reduced, allowing increasing the back diffusion effect from cathode to anode and, therefore, an improving the membrane hydration and proton conductivity. On the other hand, the use of down-slanted channels in the cathode sides did not seem to improve the water management as flooding effects were observed along the channels.

The new technological breakthrough for PEMFC research has recently focused in the new and more efficient design of bipolar plates that are the key component in fuel cell. Researchers have begun to investigate new flow field designs inspired in nature [91-94], the so-called biomimetic design. This new design drew its inspiration from nature, in other words, it reproduces the structure seen in plant tissues or leaves, and animal lungs to allow the gases to flow through the plate in a more efficient way. However, nowadays there exists little approach on how these new designs should be fabricated and therefore most research has been carried out following a bio-mimic flow field design where, starting from typical flow field designs (serpentine, interdigitated and slotted-interdigitated), changes have been incorporated by optimizing the depth and/or width of the channels to achieve the expected performance of the channels and to mimic the nature fluid dynamics.

In Roshandel et al. [95] a comparative study was carried out between parallel, serpentine and a new bipolar plate design inspired from the existed biological fluid flow patterns (Figs. 23 and 24). The results indicated that the bio inspired pattern showed more uniform fuel rates and pressure profiles on catalyst surface. With the new design, the obtained power density was higher than serpentine and parallel flow channels; up to 26% and 56% respectively.

Recent studies analyse completely different geometries from the traditional flat bipolar plates. Khazaei et al. [96,97] studied

the PEMFC performance with annular cross-section (Fig. 25). The results showed that increasing the number of connection between diffusing layers and bipolar plates enhances the fuel cell performance. In Cano-Andrade et al. [98] flow fields with 4, 8 and 12 radial channels were studied, as shown in Fig. 26. Other studies [99,100] were dedicated to the analysis of the influence of the number of channels on the PEMFC performance with flow fields with channels following a spiral design (Fig. 27).

8. Conclusions

Throughout this review it has been shown that the geometric parameters of the flow fields can have great influence on the overall PEMFC behaviour. Many of the PEMFC drawbacks discussed here may be overcome by appropriately choosing the flow field design. Thus, problems in mass transport, water management, and mal-distribution of reactants can be solved by efficiently design the BP flow fields and so, enhance PEMFC performance. For instance, homogeneous gas distribution in the flow channel can provide a uniform current density throughout the active area and, therefore, a uniform temperature distribution, causing less mechanical stresses in the MEA and prolonging the PEMFC lifetime. Therefore, flow field design is crucial for achieving high performance of the PEM fuel cell.

As many of the PEMFC operating conditions found throughout this review were not comparable, it seems impossible to set a direct comparison between the flow field design parameters and their

influence on the PEMFC performance. Nevertheless, tables 1-9 summarize available information regarding the PEMFC operating parameters and flow field geometric variables, extracted from all the referred works appearing in this review, in order to complete the results and discussions shown all along this work. On the other hand, the heterogeneity of the variables used in this kind of studies and the lack of basic information observed in many other works make it difficult to set a comparative study of the experimental results obtained from the different researchers. However, in order to improve global PEMFC performance, this review can provide researchers with helpful guidelines as to efficiently improve their flow field design processes, as the already mentioned in the concluding section.

In optimizing the geometric parameters of the PEMFC flow fields, the following important points can be considered.

8.1 Flow field

The flow field geometric configuration has little influence on the overall PEM fuel cell performance at high operation potentials. On the contrary, at low operation potentials, it significantly affected. The flow fields that offer a lower pressure drop generally shows lower performance. With serpentine and interdigitated flow fields, it can generally achieve more uniform reactants distribution. Although the elimination of condense water in the cathode is improved, the energy required to drive the gas increases, reducing the overall performance of

the PEMFC. In serpentine type flow fields, longer straight channel segments between channel bends and narrower channels enhance convection. Also, contrary to what can be expected, an increase in the active area of the MEA results in a decrease of current density.

8.2 Flow direction

The most analysed reactants flow configurations are co, counter and cross flow. Generally, fuel cells with counter flow configuration show better membrane hydration, increasing proton conductivity, thus enhancing fuel cell performance.

8.3 Channel length and number of channels

In PEMFC with serpentine gas flow channels, longer straight channel sections produce higher increases in gas pressure between adjacent channels, which enhances under rib convection and fuel cell performance. Generally, in this type of geometries, flow fields with rectangular shapes operate better than the squared ones. In addition, flow fields designs with shorter path lengths or larger number of parallel channels have better reactants distribution than flow fields with longer path channels or shorter number of parallel channels.

8.4 Use of baffles in the flow direction

Most of the results showed that due to the blockage that baffles create to the gas flow, larger amount of gas is forced to flow through the GDL to the catalyst layer due to convection effects. This increases the effective active area. However, the baffled designs showed significantly worse transient response compared to their not baffled counterparts. Moreover, it was observed that as the pressure drop increases, the global performance of the fuel cell decreases.

8.5 Cross section shape

Rectangular is still the most commonly used cross-section channel design for bipolar plates. Other cross-section shapes may show improvements in some specific aspects of the fuel cell operation.

8.6 Channel and rib width

Generally, narrower gas flow channels produce better results. The optimal rib width largely depends on PEM fuel cell operation conditions and the type of oxidising agent used. Thus, Fuel cells operating at high potentials, display better performance with wider ribs. On the other hand, in fuel cells operating with air as oxidising agent, the rib width must be smaller than that for fuel cells operating with pure oxygen.

8.7 Channel depth

In serpentine gas flow channels, reductions in flow channel height, especially at the cathode outlet, improves the mass transfer towards the diffusing layers, promotes water elimination, enhance the electrochemical reaction and increase the fuel efficiency, allowing better results in fuel cell performance.

Variations in the channel height only show appreciable effect when operating at low potentials, increasing the current densities. The main disadvantage is that the pressure drop increases, which reduces the overall system efficiency.

8.8 Height to width ratio of the channel cross section:

In the case of flow fields with serpentine gas flow channels and at high operating voltages, the performance of a PEM fuel cell can be improved as the height to width channel ratio increases.

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Table 1. Nomenclature.

Nomenclature	
Ref	Reference
Ff	Flow field
Ra, cm ²	Reactive area
Ccs, mm ²	Channel cross sectional
W _r , mm	Rib width
Ch	Channel
L _c , m	Channel length
h _c	Depth channel
W _c	Channel width
P, atm	Pressure
T _c , °C	Cell Temperature
Dp, °C	Dew point
HR, %	Relative humidity
Ox	Oxidant
Stoich	Stoichiometry
Ut%	Utilization %
I _{fr}	Inlet flow rate
HT, °C	humidification Temperature
Stat	Stationary
Aut	Automotive
a	Anode
c	Cathode
Nch	Number of channels
NA	Information not available
NS	Numerical study
EA	Experimental analysis

Table 2. Flow field design parameters.

[Ref] EA/NS	Flow field	Ra (cm ²)	Ccs h _c x w _c (mm ²)	Rw w _r (mm)	L _c (m)	P (atm) (a/c)	T (°C)	Dp (°C) or HR (%)	Ox	Stoich (a/c)	Comments
[14] EA	Parallel and interdigitated	100	NA	NA	NA	1/1	22-25	NA	O ₂	a: 0.9 A/cm ² c: 1.05 A/cm ² equivalent rate	2 mg Pt/cm ² , Nafion 115
[18] EA	Single serpentine	25	3.0 x 3.0 2.5 x 2.5 2.0 x 2.0 1.5 x 1.5	3.0 2.5 2.0 1.5	NA	Range 1–3	Range 30–80	Range 30–80	Air	1.5/2	Double cell stack
[21] NS	Single serpentine	480	1.1	-	1.2	1	70	Range 0–100%	Air	1.2/2	3-D simulation of a large-scale PEMFC
[22] EA	Single serpentine	50 100 200 300 441	0.8 x 0.8 1 x 1.1 0.85 x 0.9 0.9 x 0.8 0.8 x 1	0.8 1 0.8 0.9 0.75	3.28 4.78 3.83 3.85 4.05	3	80	100%	Air	1.5/3	A flow channel design procedure
[23] EA	Interdigitated	50	1.14 x 0.889	0.808	63.4	Range 1– 3.72	Range 40–90	Range 40–90	Air	1.21/2.65	Influence of T, P, HR and flow rate
[24] EA	Interdigitated, Mesh, Single serpentine	5	0.2 x 0.5 0.2 x 2 0.2 x 0.25	NA	22.5·10 ⁻³	1, 1.5, 2	25, 35, 50	NA	Air	NA	Micro PEMFC Influence of T, P and flow configuration
[25] NS	Parallel Interdigitated		0.5 x 0.7		6·10 ⁻²	1/1.5	80	NA	NA	NA	3-D numerical analysis

[Ref] EA/NS	Flow field	Ra (cm ²)	Ccs h _c x w _c (mm ²)	Rw w _r (mm)	L _c (m)	P (atm) (a/c)	T (°C)	Dp (°C) or HR (%)	Ox	Stoich (a/c)	Comments
[26] NS	NINO	7.29	1 x 3	3	27·10 ⁻³	1	80	NA	Air	1/1.68	2-D model
[27] NS	Parallel (co-flow) Parallel (counter flow) Interdigitated Foam	NA	1 x 0.5	1	0.1	1	80	30%	O ₂	1.5, 3, 5	3-D model. Only cathodic study
[28] EA	Parallel Serpentine Z-type	198.81	0.1 x 0.1	0.1	14.1 41.3 20.6	NA	NA	NA	Air O ₂	NA	Cathode fuel flow rate study and effects of channel number, channel length, corner numbers and baffle.
[29] EA	Parallel Interdigitated	198.81	NA	NA	NA	NA	Range 40-70	70 (a) 40-75 (c)	Air O ₂	NA	Influence of cathode flow rate, cathode inlet T, fuel cell T and cathode flow field.
[30] NS	Serpentine Parallel Multiparallel Interdigitated	58.06	1.58 x 1.58	1.58	NA	2	77	NA	Air	NA	Analysis of steady and transient state.
[31] NS	Single serpentine, parallel serpentine, single Z, U-type, parallel discontinuous and interdigitated	NA	0.72 x 2	2	NA	1.97	NA	NA	NA	1.6/3.2	Pressure drop and flow distribution
[32] NS	Single serpentine, parallel and grid	24.6	1.2 x (1- 1.8)	1.2	NA	1	50	100%	O ₂	NA	3-D model. Effects of different flow channel designs. Counter- flow

[Ref] EA/NS	Flow field	Ra (cm ²)	Ccs h _c x w _c (mm ²)	Rw w _r (mm)	L _c (m)	P (atm) (a/c)	T (°C)	Dp (°C) or HR (%)	Ox	Stoich (a/c)	Comments
[33] NS	Serpentine: (single channel, double channel, cyclic-single channel and symmetric-single channel)	10	1 x 0.8	0.8	NA	1	70	50-100%	Air	1.2/2	3-D model. High and low inlet humidity. Co-flow
[34] NS	Single, double and triple serpentine	5.29	1 x 0.766 1 x 1 1 x 1.15	1.25 1 0.836	NA	1	50	100%	O ₂	NA	3-D model. Anode parallel flow field (1 x 1). Miniature PEMFC. Influence of number of bends and channel width ratio.
[35] NS	U-type	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Analytical model for pressure drop and flow distribution
[36] NS	Parallel Z-type Serpentine (4 channel)	5.29	1 x 1	1	23·10 ⁻³ 35·10 ⁻³ 70·10 ⁻³	1	50	100%	Air	NA	3-D model. Velocity, oxygen mass fraction, current density, liquid water, and pressure distribution.
[37] NS	Z-type, U-type	15.75, 30.75	0.6 x 1.5	1.5	50·10 ⁻³	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Analytical model Analogy between fluid flow and electrical network
[38] EA	Interdigitated Single serpentine	16	1 x 2 1 x 1	1	40·10 ⁻³ 0.84	1	60	100%	Air	NA	Co-flow
[39] EA	Parallel discontinuous, cascade-type	49	2 x 1	1	NA	NA	60	100%	O ₂	1.5/2	Comparison of water management

[Ref] EA/NS	Flow field	Ra (cm ²)	Ccs h _c x w _c (mm ²)	Rw w _r (mm)	L _c (m)	P (atm) (a/c)	T (°C)	Dp (°C) or HR (%)	Ox	Stoich (a/c)	Comments
[40] NS	Parallel, interdigitated, single serpentine	1.21, 4.41, 9.61, 16.81	1 x 1	1	NA	1	50	100%	Air	NA	3-D model. Influence of the active area. As the active area was increased from 1.21 to 16.81 cm ² (increased by 13.9 times) for parallel cell, the average current density decreases by 10.6% at 0.4 V and by 11.6% at 0.3 V.
[41] NS	Single serpentine (curvilinear bends and square bends), double serpentine	25	1, 1.2, 2	NA	NA	2	NA	NA	NA	NA	3-D model. Only fluid dynamics
[42] EA	Single serpentine	50	2 x 2	2		1, 2, 3	70	85	O ₂ Air	NA	A single channel serpentine flow field is used to separately measure the current density under the land and channel
[43] EA	Parallel discount. (2 ch) Single serpentine Parallel discount. (3 ch) Multi parallel	2.25	0.3 x 0.75 0.3x0.375 0.3x0.375 0.3x0.375	0.75 0.375 0.375 0.375	38.25 212.25 116.25 22.88	1	20	100%	Air	NA	Micro PEMFC
[44] NS	Parallel discontinuous, parallel, pin-type	50	1.5 x 1.5	2	NA	1	150	NA	O ₂	NA	3-D model. High temperature PEMFC

[Ref] EA/NS	Flow field	Ra (cm ²)	Ccs h _c x w _c (mm ²)	Rw w _r (mm)	L _c (m)	P (atm) (a/c)	T (°C)	Dp (°C) or HR (%)	Ox	Stoich (a/c)	Comments
[45] NS	Single serpentine: Single inlet Multi-inlet	100	1.4 x 1 0.8 x 1	NA	NA	1	50	10,30,50,70%	O ₂	1.2/2.6	3-D model. Counterflow
[46] EA	Parallel, serpentine, interdigitated, mesh- type	5.06	0.2 x 0.3	0.3	NA	1	25, 50, 75	70%	Air	NA	Micro PEMFC
[47] EA	Multi-serpentine (5) Multi-serpentine(4) Parallel	50	1 x 1 1 x 1.5 1 x 1	1	NA	1	160	NA	Air	NA	High temperature. Effects of fuel composition ambient pressure
[48] NS	Symmetric flow, single serpentine	25	1.2 x 0.9	1.4	NA	2	70	100%	Air	1.5/2	in order to optimize the reduction of pressure drop in the gas flow channels (for the symmetric patterns) an entropy minimization criterion was applied
[49] EA	Parallel discontinuous, pin-type, parallel, interdigitated	49	1 x 1.5	2	NA	1	125	NA	O ₂ Air	NA	High temperature PEMFC
[50] NS	Interdigitated, serpentine, spiral interdigitated	1.96	0.01-0.25	NA	NA	1	50	100%	Air	NA	3-D model. Scaling effects of various flow micro channels (<100µm)
[53] NS	Parallel, interdigitated	NA	1 x 0.67 1 x 1 1 x 1.33	1.33 1 0.67	100	1	50	100%	Air	NA	3-D, two-phase, transient PEMFC model

[Ref] EA/NS	Flow field	Ra (cm ²)	Ccs h _c x w _c (mm ²)	Rw w _r (mm)	L _c (m)	P (atm) (a/c)	T (°C)	Dp (°C) or HR (%)	Ox	Stoich (a/c)	Comments
[54] NS	Parallel, Z-type, serpentine	5.29	NA	NA	NA	NA	50	100%	Air	65cm ³ min ⁻¹ and 175cm ³ min ⁻¹	3-D transient numerical model of PEMFC with different cathode flow field designs

Table 3. Flow direction.

[Ref] EA/NS	Flow direction	Ra (cm ²)	Ccs h _c x w _c (mm ²)	W _r (mm)	P (atm) (a/c)	T (°C)	Dp (° C) or HR (%) a/c	Ox	Stoich (a/c)	Comments
[55] NS	Co-flow and Counter-flow	140	NA	NA	Range (4-6)	Range 40-80	Range (0- 100%)	O ₂	1.5/2	Compared to the co-flow, counter-flow mode improves the current density distribution with dry or low humidity gases
[56] EA	Co-, cross- and counter-flow	100	NA x 0.7	1	1	NA	dry/45	Air	70%	Counter flow shows better performance (dry anode, humidified cathode);5 cell stack; flow fields investigated: serpentine (anode, and cathode), pattern type (anode);
[57] EA	Co-flow and Counter-flow	25	1.2 x 1.2	0.8	2.96/2.96	80	0/0 %	O ₂	1.2/1.5	Counter flow shows better performance; with different O ₂ /H ₂ inlet/outlets to study the effect of gravity;

Table 4. Channel length and number of channels.

[Ref] EA/NS	L_c (cm) and Nch	Ra (cm^2)	Ccs $h_c \times w_c$ (mm^2)	W_r (mm)	P (atm) (a/c)	T ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	Dp ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) or HR (%) a/c	Ox	Stoich (a/c)	Comments
[59] NS	NA	NA	NA x 1	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA/2	Convective bypass can be increased in single-serpentine flow field geometries by simply increasing de length of the flow channel. Analytical model. Only cathodic analysis
[60] NS	Nch: 3-,6- 13- and 26-	200	0.55x0.9	0.9	1/1	70	80/70 $^{\circ}\text{C}$	O ₂	1.2/2	3-D model. The shorter path length gives more uniform current density distribution and less condensed liquid water than the longer path

Table 5. Use of baffles.

[Ref] EA/NS	Use of baffles	L_c (m)	Ra (cm^2)	Ccs $h_c \times w_c$ (mm^2)	W_r (mm)	P (atm) (a/c)	T_c ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	Dp ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) or HR (%) or HT ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) a/c	Ox	Stoich (a/c) Ifr (a/c) $\text{cm}^3\text{min}^{-1}$	Comments
[61] NS	1-9	0.04	NA	NA	NA	NA	60	NA	NA	NA	PEMFC 2-D half-cell model; partially blocked fuel flow channels
[62] NS	1-5	0.0762	NA	NAx0.762	NA	NA	80	100%	Air	NA	2-D fuel cell model
[63] NS	Three different triple serpentine-baffle flow field designs	NA	5.29	1x1	1	NA	50	100%	Air	260/700	At low operating voltages better performance in baffle design; Baffles added at the inlet, outlet and at the center of serpentine flow fields; 3-D model

[Ref] EA/NS	Use of baffles	L_c (m)	Ra (cm^2)	Ccs $h_c \times w_c$ (mm^2)	W_r (mm)	P (atm) (a/c)	T_c ($^{\circ}C$)	Dp ($^{\circ}C$) or HR (%) or HT ($^{\circ}C$) a/c	Ox	Stoich (a/c) lfr (a/c) $cm^3 min^{-1}$	Comments
[64] NS	Baffle-blocked flow field designs	0.0762	NA	0.0762x0.0762	NA	1/1	80	20%, 60%, 100 % for both a and c	Air	lfr:175/175	Humidity effects study; Baffle blockage effect enhance PEMFC performance; 2-D numerical model; There is an optimum number of baffles that increases cell performance
[65] EA	Interdigitated flow channels with baffles at the end and/or at the center of the flow channels	0.141	198.81	1x1 1x0.8 1x1.2	1 1.2 0.8	0.96/0.96	50	70 $^{\circ}C$ /65 $^{\circ}C$	O ₂ Air	lfr/c:1500 lfr/a:400-3000(O ₂); 1000-4000(Air)	Experimental polarization curves; three flow area ratios for each flow field design
[66] EA	Conventional interdigitated and mid-baffle interdigitated flow field	NA	50	NA	NA	1-2	Slightly below humidifier temperature to avoid membrane dehydration	HT: 80/90	O ₂ Air	lfr a: 457	Experimental polarization and power density curves; different oxidant gas flow rates and operating pressures

Table 6. Cross sectional shape.

[Ref] EA/NS	Cross sectional shape	Ra (cm ²)	Ccs h _c x W _c (mm ²)	W _r (mm)	P (atm) (a/c)	T _c (°C)	Dp (°C) or HR (%) a/c	Ox	Stoich (a/c)	Comments
[68] NS	Rectangular, triangular and hemispherical	16	h _c , W _c range: 0.5, 1, 1.5, 2, 3, 4	Range 0.5, 1, 1.5, 2, 3, 4	2	77	NA	NA	NA	Hydrogen consumption as parameter to judge the performance of the fuel cell; the optimum dimension values for W _c , W _r and h _c was close to 1.5, 0.5 and 1.5 mm, respectively; a 3-D half-cell model; 216 cases
[69] NS	Rectangular, trapezoidal and parallelogram	Range: 0.3173- 0.5076	1x(1, 0.9, 0.8)	0.7,0.8	1/1	70	100%	O ₂	1.2/2.0	3-D non-isothermal model; single straight channel geometry (34.7 mm); optimum channel-rib width ratio (1.3-1.4) at high operating current density
[70] EA	Rectangular and triangular channels	50	0.76x1.37	1.45	1.97	80	100%	Air	2/2	Effects of flow field and diffusion layer properties on water accumulation measured by neutron radiography method; Serpentine flow field pattern

[Ref] EA/NS	Cross sectional shape	Ra (cm ²)	Ccs h _c x W _c (mm ²)	W _r (mm)	P (atm) (a/c)	T _c (°C)	Dp (°C) or HR (%) a/c	Ox	Stoich (a/c)	Comments
[71] NS	Three tasks: 1 st cross section with four different draft angles; 2 nd four different radiuses at channel bending areas; 3 rd effect of channel depth uniformity	1 st 2.54 cm ² 2 nd 2.54 cm ² 3 rd 25 cm ²	1 st 0.44, 0.50, 0.52, 0.63 2 nd Sharp angle, 0.3 mm, 0.6 mm , 1 mm 3 rd Variable channel depht (0.4 mm average)	variable	Stat: 1 Aut: 2.7	70	Stat: 80°C/70°C Aut: 75%RH/80°C dry	Stat: Air Aut: Air	Stat: 1.2/2.0 Aut: 1.3/2.0	3-D model. Effect of channel tolerances on performance; operating conditions for stationary and automotive applications

Table 7. Channel and rib width.

[Ref] EA/NS	Flow field configuration	Ra (cm ²)	Ccs h _c x W _c (mm ²)	W _r (mm)	P (atm) (a/c)	T _c (°C)	Dp (°C) or HR (%) a/c	Ox	Stoich or Ut% or Ifr (a/c)	Comments
[72] EA	NA	80	NAx1	Range 0.5-3	1/1	65	Humidified condition (100%) humidifier T 80°C: Dry condition: humidifier T 50°C	Air	Ut%: 80%/40%	Dry and humidified cases; In both cases the narrower the rib width, the more improved the performance of the cell;
[73] NS	NA	NA	NA	Half channel land width: 0.5 mm Half channel width: 0.5 mm	1.5/1.5	80	NA	O ₂	NA	2-D catalyst agglomerate model; effect of channel-to-land ratio on current density

[Ref] EA/NS	Flow field configuration	Ra (cm ²)	Ccs h _c x W _c (mm ²)	W _r (mm)	P (atm) (a/c)	T _c (°C)	Dp (°C) or HR (%) a/c	Ox	Stoich or Ut% or Ifr (a/c)	Comments
[74] NS	Anode: serpentine flow field Cathode: straight channel; three different widths of channels	34	Cathode channel width: 2,3, and 4 mm; Anode channel configuration fixed	1	1/1	H ₂ inlet T: 26°C	The air supply to cathode was spontaneously obtained by natural convection from environmental air without external heating and humidity	Air	1/natural convection from the environmental	3D mathematical model; effect of cathode channel configuration.; air-breathing PEMFC
[75] NS	Straight channel model	NA	NA	NA	NA	65	100%	NA	NA	3-Dmodel; 18 cases calculation; cathode h _c /anode h _c ratio; channel/land ratio at cathode and anode side; offset ratio between cathode and anode channel.

[Ref] EA/NS	Flow field configuration	Ra (cm ²)	Ccs h _c x W _c (mm ²)	W _r (mm)	P (atm) (a/c)	T _c (°C)	Dp (°C) or HR (%) a/c	Ox	Stoich or Ut% or lfr (a/c)	Comments
[76] EA	Three different designs with different land and channel widths: 2/3, 2/2 and 1/1	a: standard 50 cm ² serpentine flow field; c: serpentine flow field with only two channels and one land area	NAx3,2,1	2,1	atmospheric	70	100%/100%	Air O ₂	NA	Technique to separately measure current density under the land and channel; an optimized flow field should have narrow channels.
[77] EA/NS	Parallel flow field design; three different channel/rib width ratios	100	NAx0.5-1	0.5-1.5	Ambient outlet pressure	55-60	Dry anode/45°C	Air	Ut%: 70/25	An optimum between 0.7 and 1 mm was found for either channel or rib widths; influence of channel geometries on stack performance; counter flow

[Ref] EA/NS	Flow field configuration	Ra (cm ²)	Ccs h _c x W _c (mm ²)	W _r (mm)	P (atm) (a/c)	T _c (°C)	Dp (°C) or HR (%) a/c	Ox	Stoich or Ut% or lfr (a/c)	Comments
[78] NS	Serpentine flow field; triple channel design: 0.9/0.9; 1.0/0.7; 0.7/1.0	25	NAx0.70.9, 1.0,	0.9-1.0	Stat:101 kPa Aut: 274 kPa	Stat:70 Aut:80	Stat:80°C/70°C Aut: 75%/80°C dry	Air	St:1.2/2.0 Au:1.3/2.0	Three different widths of channel/rib; two identical flow field patterns; stationary and automotive conditions; 3-D model
[79] NS	Parallel and interdigitated flow channel design	5.29	NAx0.575- 1.342	0.627- 1.464	1/1	50	100%	O ₂	lfr/a: 260 cm ³ min ⁻¹ ; lfr/c 700 cm ³ min ⁻¹	3-D model; five different flow channel area ratio

Table 8. Channel depth and height to width ratio of the channel cross section.

[Ref] EA/NS	Flow field configuration	Ra (cm ²)	Ccs h _c x W _c (mm ²)	W _r (mm)	L _c (m)	P (atm) (a/c)	T (°C)	Dp (°C) or HR (%)	Ox	Stoich (a/c)	Comments
[80] NS	Straight flow channel tapered in height or width	NA	1 x 1	NA	0.141	1	50	100%	Air	NA	3-D model. With the pressure loss considered, however, the best performance can be obtained at the height taper ratio ($\lambda_x = H_{out}/H_{in}$) of 0.5 and the width taper ratio ($\lambda_z = W_{out}/W_{in}$) of 1.8
[81] NS	Straight flow channel tapered in height	NA	0.762 x w _c	NA	0.762	1	80	100%	Air	NA	2-D model. ($R_{ch} = Depth_{out}/Depth_{in} = 1, 0.5, 0.1$) With the reduction in the channel depth along the streamwise direction, the reactant fuel gas in the tapered channel can be accelerated as well as forced into the gas diffuser layer to enhance the electrochemical reaction.
[82] NS	Multi serpentine (4) (outlet channel contraction)	5.29	1 x 1	1	$70.1 \cdot 10^{-3}$	NA	50	100%	Air	NA	3-D model. The height contraction ratio of the outlet channel, δ_H , is defined as $\delta_H = H_c/H_o$, and the length contraction ratio of the outlet channel, δ_L , is defined as $\delta_L = L_c/L_o$. When the pressure losses are also taken into account, the optimal performance is obtained at a height contraction ratio of 0.4 and a length contraction ratio of 0.4

[Ref] EA/NS	Flow field configuration	Ra (cm ²)	Ccs h _c x W _c (mm ²)	W _r (mm)	L _c (m)	P (atm) (a/c)	T (°C)	Dp (°C) or HR (%)	Ox	Stoich (a/c)	Comments
[83] NS	Single serpentine (tapered and diverging channels)	0.81	1 x 1	1	49·10 ⁻³	NA	50	100%	NA	NA	3-D, two-phase, non-isothermal model. The optimal flow design (H0 (1mm)> H4 (0.81mm)> H1 (0.33mm)> H2≈H3 (0.1mm)) yields W _{cell} = 9275 W·m ⁻² , accounting for the 11.9% increase in cell power density. The optimal channel design has three tapered channels (channels 2–4) and one diverging channel, channel 5
[84] NS	Single serpentine (variable heights and widths)	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	50	100%	NA	NA	3-D, two-phase, non-isothermal model. The optimization results show that flow channels 1, 3 and 4 are tapered flow channels, while flow channels 2 and 5 are diverging flow channels. The widths of flow channels 1–3 gradually increase, while the widths of flow channels 3–5 gradually decrease. The best cell performance is P _{cell} = 8894 W·m ⁻² , 22.5% better than for the basic design
[85] NS	Straight flow channel tapered in height	NA	h _c x 1	NA	0.05	1	80	NA	NA	NA	3-D model. The numerical results were reported for three different flow channel angles of inclination, that is, θ _{FC} = 0°, 0.5° and 0.75°. The main disadvantage of the use of non-uniform channels is the pressure drop increase. For θ _{FC} = 0.75° the pressure drop increased by a factor of almost 3.5 times, while for θ _{FC} = 0.5° this reduced to a factor of two.

[Ref] EA/NS	Flow field configuration	Ra (cm ²)	Ccs h _c x W _c (mm ²)	W _r (mm)	L _c (m)	P (atm) (a/c)	T (°C)	Dp (°C) or HR (%)	Ox	Stoich (a/c)	Comments
[86] NS	Multi serpentine (5)	25	0.34x1 0.5x1 0.67x1 0.83x1 0.34x1.25 0.34x1.5 0.34x1.75	1 1 1 1 0.75 0.5 0.25	NA	1	75	100%	Air	1.5/2	3-D model. As the h _c increases, the pressure drop is decreased because of the greater cross-sectional area for gas flow, and the decreased pressure drop results in the reduction of the load of BOP and accumulation of liquid water at the outlet. As the W _c increases, the extent of the pressure drop becomes lower due to smaller difference of the cross sectional area and liquid water is removed faster than when the channel height increases (because of the smaller rib width)
[87] NS	Single serpentine	2.56	0.27x4 0.4x2.66 0.53x2 0.67x1.6 0.8x1.33 1.33x0.8 1.6x0.67 2x0.53 2.66x0.4 4x0.27	1.33	NA	1	70	100%	Air	1.2/2	3-D model. Ccs (1.06 mm ²), W _r (1.33) and Ra (2.56 cm ²) were maintained constant. C _H /C _W (Channel height/width): 02/30, 03/20, 04/15, 05/12, 06/10, 10/06, 12/05, 15/04, 20/03 and 30/02. (C _H < C _W) less uniform, (C _H > C _W) more uniform The 10/06 and 12/05 present the best combination of variables

Table 9. New flow field geometries for bipolar plates.

[Ref] EA/NS	Flow field configuration	Ra (cm ²)	Ccs h _c x w _c (mm ²)	W _r (mm)	L _c (m)	P (atm) (a/c)	T (°C)	Dp (°C) or HR (%)	Ox	Stoich (a/c)	Comments
[88] NS	Slotted- interdigitated	NA	0.5 x 1	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	3-D CFD. For stamped thin metal is more suitable than serpentine flow field
[89] NS	Straight and wave- like	NA	0.5 x 0.5	0.5	0.1	1	50, 60, 70	100%	Air	NA	3-D model. In general, the results have shown that compared to a straight gas flow channel, the wave-like channel provides an improved convective heat transfer performance, a higher gas flow velocity and a more uniform temperature distribution
[90] EA	Parallel discontinuous slanted channels	70.5	1 x 1	1	NA	NA	80	81% 148% 179%	Air	1.2/2	The experimental results showed that modifying the anode flow field using down- slanted channels provided higher cell performance. Water concentration at the gas diffusion layer is reduced resulting in more back diffusion of water from the cathode to anode, thus inducing membrane hydration and improving the conductivity
[91] NS	Serpentine	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	80	NA	O ₂	NA	The objectives were to find the optimal structure of the gas flow distributor in the cell, as seen from the perspective of energy efficiency of the whole cell, and to determine the minimum amount of catalyst (in this case, Pt) in the electrocatalytic layer
[92] NS/EA	Biometric flow field	24.6	1 x 1.2	1	$50 \cdot 10^{-3}$	NA	50	100%	O ₂	550/572 cm ³ ·min ⁻¹	Biometric vs. serpentine and parallel flow field

[Ref] EA/NS	Flow field configuration	Ra (cm ²)	Ccs h _c x w _c (mm ²)	W _r (mm)	L _c (m)	P (atm) (a/c)	T (°C)	Dp (°C) or HR (%)	Ox	Stoich (a/c)	Comments
[94] NS/EA	Simple serpentine, interdigitated, leaf flow pattern and lung flow pattern	25	1.016 x 0.7874	0.8	NA	Range 1-3	Range 35-38	Range 0-100%	Air	NA	3-D, isothermal model. The optimum operating conditions of 65-75 °C cell temperature, 2 atm backpressure, and 100% HR are found for the new leaf and lung designs
[95] NS	Parallel, single serpentine, bio inspired (BI)	25	1 x 2	1	NA	1	50	100%	Air	NA	3-D model. In proposed BI bipolar plate the power density is higher than parallel and serpentine flow channels up to 56% and 26% respectively
[96] NS	Annular shaped	1	NA	NA	$12 \cdot 10^{-3}$	1	70	NA	O ₂	NA	3-D, single phase model. The results show that the cell performance is increased as the number of connections between GDL and bipolar plate increases.
[97] NS	Annular shaped	1	NA	NA	$12 \cdot 10^{-3}$	1	70	NA	O ₂	NA	3-D, single phase model. The results show that by increasing the thickness and decreasing the porosity of GDL the performance of the cell enhances. Also the results show that by decreasing the thickness of the membrane the performance of the cell increases.
[98]	Radial flow field	10.54	1 x	NA	$20 \cdot 10^{-3}$	1	70	100%	NA	NA	Three different cases: 4, 8 and 12-channel model A comparison of the three cases shows that the 4-channel model has the optimal performance, i.e., it provides the highest current density production with the smallest pressure drop along the channel length.

[Ref] EA/NS	Flow field configuration	Ra (cm ²)	Ccs h _c x w _c (mm ²)	W _r (mm)	L _c (m)	P (atm) (a/c)	T (°C)	Dp (°C) or HR (%)	Ox	Stoich (a/c)	Comments
[99] NS	Fermet spiral	NA	1 x 0.8	NA	NA	1	70	NA	NA	NA	<p>3-D model. A new dimensionless parameter to represent the ratio of the entropy generation due to mass transfer to the total entropy generation. Results demonstrate that the main sources of irreversibility in a fuel cell are the concentration losses for the most part of the operational domain, whereas the heat transfer effect is not dominant.</p> <p>At high humidity conditions the entropy generation is high but the highest density production is reached</p>
[100]	Archimedes' spiral	16.6	1 x 0.8	NA	NA	2	70	100%	Air	1.5/2	<p>3-D, non-isothermal, single phase model. Two different parameters were used to compare the cell performance based on the entropy analysis, the Bejan number and the Π number.</p> <p>Bejan number is the ratio of heat transfer irreversibility to total irreversibility due to heat transfer and fluid friction.</p> <p>Π number is the ratio of entropy generation due to the matter flow to the total entropy. The number of channels used considerably affects the cell performance, finding the optimal value between 3 or 4 channels</p>

Fig. 1 - Different geometrical configurations of the gas flow field: a) Serpentine flow field channel (single); b) Straight parallel flow field channel or Z-type parallel configuration; c) Interdigitated flow field channel.

Fig. 2 - Different geometrical configurations of the gas flow field: a) Pin-type flow field channel; b) Cascade flow field channel.

Fig. 3 - Picture of the gas flow design machined on the bipolar plate. Drawn from [22].

Fig. 4 - Gas flow field studied: a) Interdigitated flow field channel; b) Pin-type flow field channel; c) Serpentine flow field channel. Drawn from [24].

Fig. 5 - Schematic diagram of gas flow in different flow fields: a) Conventional parallel flow field channel; b) Interdigitated flow field channel. Drawn from [52].

Fig. 6 - Flow fields analyzed: a) Serpentine flow field (single); b) Serpentine flow field (multiple); c) Parallel flow field; d) U-type parallel flow field; e) U-type symmetric flow field; f) Parallel in series (discontinuous type); g) Interdigitated flow field. Drawn from [31].

Fig. 7 - Different flow direction schemes: a) Counter flow; b) Cross flow; c) Co-flow. Drawn from [56].

Fig. 8 - Gas flow field with cascade channels on 100 cm² reactive area. Drawn from [58].

Fig. 9 - Flow field patterns of anode and cathode on 200 cm² PEMFC: a) 3-channel multiple serpentine flow-field; b) 6-channel multiple serpentine flow-field; c) 13-channel multiple serpentine flow-field; d) 26-channel multiple serpentine flow-field; e) 26-channel multiple symmetric serpentine flow-field. Drawn from [60].

Fig. 10 - Flow convection under rib through gas diffusion layers.

Fig. 11 - Schematic diagram of the analyzed flow fields :a) Parallel flow field; b) Interdigitated flow field I with a baffle located at one end of each flow path; c) Interdigitated flow field II with baffles located at the mid-way/ends of each flow path. Drawn from [65].

Fig. 12 - Schematic diagram of the analyzed flow fields: a) Conventional interdigitated flow field; b) Mid-baffle interdigitated flow field. Drawn from [66].

Fig. 13 - Cross-sectional view of different geometrical configurations analyzed: a) Rectangular; b) Trapezoidal; c) Parallelogram. Drawn from [69].

Fig. 14 - Cross-sectional view of analyzed channels. Drawn from [70].

Fig. 15 - 25 cm² flow field with different widths of channel/rib. Drawn from [78].

Fig. 16 - Schematic diagram of the 2D PEMFC model. Drawn from [81].

Fig. 17 - Schematic diagram of flow channel with contracted outlet channel height. Drawn from [82].

Fig. 18 - Serpentine flow field with varying channel heights. Drawn from [83].

Fig. 19 - Three-dimensional view of straight single channel fuel model. Drawn from [85].

Fig. 20 - Seven 25 cm² multiple serpentine flow fields (5 channels) with different channel widths and heights. Drawn from [86].

Fig. 21 - Geometric configuration of analyzed models: a) Models with horizontal cross section; b) Models with vertical cross section; c) Diagram of the cross section and parameters: C_H : Channel height, C_W : Channel width, R_W : Rib width, L_y : Width of the reactive area. Drawn from [87].

Fig. 22 - New geometry with wave-like gas flow fields channels. Drawn from [89].

Fig. 23 - Tree leaf as an example of fluid distribution pattern in nature.

Fig. 24 - Comparison of different flow fields: a) Parallel flow channels; b) Serpentine flow channels; c) Bio inspired flow channel. Drawn from [95].

Fig. 25 - Schematic diagram of an annular PEMFC. Drawn from [96].

Fig. 26 - Schematic diagram of a radial PEMFC with 8 channels.
Drawn from [98].

Fig. 27 - Schematic diagram of a PEMFC with 8 spiral channels.
Drawn from [100].

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